

Strategic Planning Element and Performance of Turkana County Government, Kenya

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Abstract: The general objective of this study was to assess the influence of strategic planning and performance in Turkana county government, Kenya. The specific objective was to determine the influence of stakeholder involvement on performance in Turkana county government, Kenya. The study was anchored on the strategic leadership theory. The total population was seventy seven respondents drawn from senior, middle and junior management from the ten departments of Turkana County government, and the sample size was the same as the target population. The study therefore adopted a census method for data collection. The study used a descriptive survey research design. Data was collected using structured questionnaires. Once ascertained, data duly collected analyzed using descriptive statistics. Correlation and ANOVA techniques using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS v29) software for establishing the influence of independent study variables and the dependent variable. The analysis results were presented in charts, and tables. The study findings revealed a statistically significant influence among variables with an F-test of 16.401 being greater than the 5% significance level adopted. The results were Shareholder involvement explained 58.6% ($t=2.139$, $r=.796$) of Performance of Turkana County government. This study will be significant to the county, national governments, institutions and non-state acting organizations.

Keywords: Strategic Planning Elements, Stakeholder Involvement.

1. INTRODUCTION

Organizational performance may be defined as an analysis of a company's performance as compared to its goals and objectives. Within corporate organizations, there are three primary outcomes analyzed: financial performance, market performance and shareholder value (Robert, *et al*, 2020). Furthermore, performance is a measure of properly using the organizational resources towards meeting the objectives and targets. It is the core of any organization, since performance is a determinant of the ability of the organization to continue its operation and survive the highly competitive market. Performance also measures the health of the competitiveness with other market players and thrives such that it can expand to other regions (Wangiru *et al*, 2020). Performance of any organization is one of the mechanisms to gain people's commitment towards achieving the stated objectives of the organization (Kigenza & Irechukwur, 2023).

Strategic planning is the process where leaders are able to spell out the vision and pinpoint the various steps to be taken in form of goal attainment to achieve it (Alosani *et al.*, 2020). Organization leaders generate new justifications for the institutional to thrive in a chaotic business environment through leadership. Further, strategic planning aligns an institution with effective plan development that produces competitive returns and also influence creation of strategic intent and mission. When performing the task of laying out strategies, the leaders ensure that they forecast and develop operational plans obtained by benchmarking with what others have achieved and once satisfied, the resources are allocated (George

et al., 2019). Strategic planning is distinct from traditional long range planning in that it sees ‘the big picture’ and focuses on purpose, values and priorities. Fundamental and conflicting organizational issues have to be identified and handled. Attention to the environment is important, and realpolitik and stakeholders must be addressed. The planning is largely dependent on county management. In order to build commitment, the planning focuses on critical issues, actions and implementation (Wangiru *et al.*, 2020). Therefore, strategic planning is intertwined with strategic management.

In Russia, Klimenko and Kalgin (2018) in strategic planning that is applied in the federal government noted that strategic management implementation helps an institution to cut down on costs and this enhances performance. According to Johansson (2017), successful project execution and achievement rely heavily on addressing the desires and expectations of those involved, and failure to do so can result in a slew of project failure issues. This idea was echoed by Georgopoulos and Tannenbaum (2017). Who contended that simply identifying stakeholders is insufficient; instead, managers and owners must value each stakeholder's interest in order to communicate their expectations on project resolutions (Njenga & Ingabire, 2021). In Brazil, Drago *et al.*, (2023) investigated how institutional performance was affected by dynamic capabilities strategic planners. Systematic Literature Review (SLR) was adopted which covered planning conduct and development of knowledge. In relation to this, Drago *et al.*, (2023) used hundred and eighteen articles whose content ranged from 2006-2021. The results revealed that the dynamic capabilities of strategic planners influenced positively and increased the competitive intensity of the organization with other institutions.

In Africa, Meyer (2017), the study in Sub Saharan African countries revealed that the strategic plan goals and objectives remain a source of guidance and focus, the implementation plan delves into the messy work of getting the job done while constant control, follow up and updates are made. Formulating a strategy is much easier than implementing it correctly and creating a brilliant strategy is nothing compared to executing it successfully. In Nigeria, Oludele (2021) assessed how healthcare institutions’ performance was impacted by strategic planning. The study was descriptive in nature and it targeted 50 staff in Nigeria’s health institutions where 30 returned the questionnaires. According to Oludele (2021), strategic planning had positive influence on performance. Kenya has an affirmative relationship as confirmed in a study conducted by Arasa (2008) for firms in the insurance sector, which tested the impact of strategic planning on organizational performance. Based on some of the studies that were carried out in Kenya, the government rolled out a string of initiatives to improve service-delivery in all its institutions. This effort culminated in the introduction of performance contracting between the Kenyan government and state corporations. A key requirement of that contracting was the development of a strategic plan.

Arasa and K’obonyo (2019) in their study on the relationship between Strategic Planning and firm performance established that the correlation analysis results indicated the existence of a strong relationship between strategic planning and firm performance. Further all the strategic planning steps, defining corporate purpose, scanning of business, environment, strategic choice and setting up of implementation, evaluation and control systems were found to be positively related to company performance. The Government of Kenya has been undertaking a series of reforms aimed at enhancing quality, efficiency and transparency in the service delivery by public sector institutions (Arasa, 2008). Among the key reforms was the Result Based Management (RBM) generally and performance contracting (PC) in particular, which have strategic planning as the main point of reference. As indicated in the “General Guidance and Direction for Negotiating the 2007/08 Performance Contracts “Strategic plan is a cornerstone for the design and development of Performance Contract” in the public sector. Strategic planning is a vehicle that facilitates improved organizational performance.

Odongo and Owori (2015) conducted a study in KEMRI, on the effect of strategic planning on organizational growth revealed that strategic planning if well implemented in the organization is effective towards growth. Strategic planning is appropriate, suitable, reasonable and acceptable to the organization. The Study indicated that KEMRI has met some of its organizational objectives through strategic planning implementation. It also revealed that budgetary allocation influenced growth in KEMRI. From the findings it clearly indicated that the budgetary allocation affected organizational growth. Strategic Planning is intended to help governments, communities, and Organizations deal with and adapt to their changing internal and external circumstances. It can help clarify and resolve the most important pressing issues they face. It enables them to build on strengths, take advantage of opportunities, and become much more effective in what seems to be a more hostile world (Shahin, 2020). Most county governments in Kenya face budget constraints, structural and capability gaps, and inadequate leadership while implementing strategies. As strategic plans are blueprints with no effect on how they are

implemented, county governments need help implementing the strategy due to the unpredictability of policy priorities, changing the focus of certain development players, budget limitations, and relationship management. While it is generally acknowledged that change is essential for an organization's development, more than 70% of change-oriented attempts in the name of change strategies fail (Wangiru *et al*, 2020). Furthermore, according to Harvard Business Review (2017), the rate of effectively applied strategies is between 10% and 30%. A common criticism of the strategic planning.

The process is that it creates a document that ends up gathering dust on a shelf because the government lacks or fails to make effective use of the valuable knowledge depicted in the strategic planning document (Barnett, 2019). Several studies have looked at the relationship between strategic planning and organizational performance. Material (2019) investigated the relationship between multidimensional strategic planning activities and firm results. A study conducted by Klimenko & Kalgin (2018) in Russia did focus on strategic planning, which the federal government had adopted. It was noted that through strategy implementation, an organization can cut down on its costs, and this improves its performance. Shimwa (2019) revealed a positive linkage between strategic planning and project performance. However, none of these studies assessed the extent to which strategic planning affects organizational performance, particularly in Turkana county government in Kenya, no analysis of stakeholder contribution in strategic planning with organization performance, and researchers did not examine if risk planning and resource allocation have a relationship with organizational performance in a county government. The specific objective of the study was to establish the influence of stakeholder involvement and performance of Turkana County government, Kenya.

2. STAKEHOLDER INVOLVEMENT AND ORGANIZATION PERFORMANCE

In the government sector, the values and expectations of different stakeholder groups in county governments play an important part in the development of strategy. As organizations strive to position themselves within turbulent environments, their strategy formulation efforts would be fruitless, more so in their implementation if pertinent stakeholders are not involved in the process. Clear understanding of the potential roles and contributions of the many different stakeholders is a fundamental pre-requisite for a successful participatory strategy formulation process. Stakeholders are those whose interests are affected by the organization's activities or those whose activities strongly affect the organization; they are those who possess information, resources and expertise needed for strategy formulation and implementation; and they are those who control relevant implementation instruments (Okoth & Miroga, 2023). Stakeholder involvement is critical for any given course of action, the strategic planning team determines. It offers important insight into planning, facilitates their "buy in" and support for the strategy, allows greater ownership, facilitates better decisions and may identify issues not addressed by the executive team (Oboko, 2018). Their involvement is a valuable prelude to the formulation of mission statements for effectiveness of strategies and critical to implementation success. The criteria stakeholders use to judge the organization's performance influence how the organization pursues strategies and manages resources effectively over the long term while increasing stakeholder satisfaction.

Stakeholders by their very definition are important to an entity; however, for practical reasons it's not possible to include all stakeholders in the actual strategic planning sessions. Although all key stakeholders cannot be involved in the actual planning sessions, they should all be involved in the process (Patterson & Radtke, 2019). In a study carried out by Neil Jeffery - Doughty Centre Associate at Cranfield University School of Management UK on Stakeholder Engagement: A Road Map to Meaningful Stakeholder Engagement, Diamond and Khemani (2020), emphasized that Stakeholder engagement is relevant to any type of organization: business, public or civil society. It is important in the context of running an organization responsibly and is integral to the concept of Corporate Responsibility. An organization cannot be serious about corporate responsibility unless it is serious about stakeholder engagement and vice versa. Stakeholder engagement is crucially different to stakeholder management: stakeholder engagement implies a willingness to listen; to discuss issues of interest to stakeholders of the Organization; and, critically, the Organization has to be prepared to consider changing what it aims to achieve and how it operates, as a result of stakeholder engagement (Diamond & Khemani, 2020).

In Russia, Klimenko and Kalgin (2018), in strategic planning that is applied in the federal government noted that strategy planning helps an institution to cut down on costs and this enhances implementation and performance. According to Johansson (2017), successful project execution and achievement rely heavily on addressing the desires and expectations of those involved, and failure to do so can result in a slew of project failure issues. This idea was echoed by Georgopoulos and Tannenbaum (2017). Who contended that simply identifying stakeholders is insufficient; instead, managers and

owners must value each stakeholder's interest in order to communicate their expectations on project resolutions (Njenga & Ingabire, 2021). In Africa, Meyer (2017), the study in Sub Saharan African countries revealed that the strategic plan goals and objectives remain a source of guidance and focus, the implementation plan delves into the messy work of getting the job done while constant control, follow up and updates are made. Formulating a strategy is much easier than implementing it correctly and creating a brilliant strategy is nothing compared to executing it successfully.

In Rwanda, according to MININFRA under stakeholder engagement plan 2021, they emphasized that SEP identifies actions required to promote productive involvement of stakeholders in decision-making and execution. It can be formal or informal and highly detailed or broadly framed, based on the needs of the project and the expectations of its stakeholders. According to the ESF and the ESS10 specifically, the SEP describes the timing and methods of engaging with stakeholders and range of information to be communicated to them as well as information to be sought from them throughout the life cycle of the project, distinguishing between Project Affected People (PAPs) and other interested parties. An effective stakeholder engagement depends on mutual trust, respect and transparent communication between the county government and its stakeholders.

Drago *et al.* (2023) investigated how institutional performance was affected by dynamic capabilities strategic planners in Brazil. The results revealed that the dynamic capabilities of strategic planners influenced positively and increased the competitive intensity of the organization with other institutions. However, Drago *et al.* (2023) relied on secondary data which is often prone to biases on authors' opinions rather than the reality and the study was carried out in a developed country compared to the scope of this study. Oludele (2021) assessed how healthcare institutions' performance was impacted by strategic planning. The study was descriptive in nature and it targeted 50 staff in Nigeria's health institutions where 30 returned the questionnaires. That notwithstanding, Oludele (2021) did not reveal how the 50-health staff that were targeted were sampled nor provided any pre-test study results to determine the reliability of the data collection questionnaires. This study was carried out in a sector other than the devolved units that this study targets.

In Kenya's private universities, Odera and Jonyo (2020) examined the impact of strategic leadership on organizational performance. Therefore, Odera and Jonyo (2020) findings on the first research question revealed that organizational performance was significantly predicted by organizational mission and vision human capital development. The study was carried out on Kenyan private university but not on the devolved units of government. Odongo and Owori (2015) conducted a study in KEMRI, on the effect of strategic planning on organizational growth revealed that strategic planning, if well implemented in the organization, is effective towards growth. Strategic planning is appropriate, suitable, reasonable and acceptable to the organization. The Study indicated that KEMRI have met some of its organization objectives through strategic planning implementation. It also revealed that budgetary allocation influenced growth in KEMRI. From the finding it clearly indicates that the budgetary allocation affects organizational growth. This study was however on an institution of government other than the devolved units. This study sought out to examine strategic planning element on organizational performance in Turkana county government, Kenya.

3. METHOD

Descriptive design is preferred because it ensures complete description and analysis of the phenomena making sure that it has minimum biasness. Descriptive survey research designs are intended to produce accurate description of variables relevant to the decisions being faced without demonstrating that some relationship exist between the variables Rost (2020). The descriptive survey research design enabled the researcher to get actual happenings and expected happenings in order to make a detailed assessment. The study's target population was 68 respondents drawn from senior, middle and junior management from the ten departments of Turkana County government, since they are involved in the development and implementation of strategic plans of their respective areas (Cannella *et al.*, 2019). The study used census sampling due to the small number of target population. The main instrument of primary data collection for this study was the questionnaires. Piloting was done to test the validity and reliability of the data collection instrument. The data was organized for process coding, tabulation and statistical computations using the Statistical package for Social Sciences (SPSS version 29). Both descriptive and inferential statistical measures were used in the analysis. Descriptive measures included: frequency tables and percentages while inferential statistical measures to be adopted will include: Pearson correlation coefficient and multiple regression analysis for the determination of the relationship between the study variables. The relationship between the variables was established and presented in a multiple regression model.

4. DISCUSSION

4.1. Stakeholder Involvement and Performance

Data on this variable was collected and tabulated as shown in the table below;

Table 1: Shareholder Involvement and Performance

Item	SA %	A %	N %	D %	SD %	Mean	STDEV
Considering stakeholder's needs and priorities during strategic planning process influence performance in the county government	35	33	7	13	12	3.124	2.158
Stakeholder participation in strategic planning process influence performance in Turkana county government	26	23	7	27	17	2.981	1.745
Stakeholder feedback during strategic planning influence performance in Turkana county government	27	29	10	21	13	2.987	1.526
Get stakeholders to understand constituents of strategic planning and performance in Turkana county government	19	18	6	28	29	3.420	1.652

The table above presented the feedback from the respondents on the stakeholder involvement variable. On whether considering stakeholder's needs and priorities during strategic planning process influence performance in the county government, 35% of the respondents strongly agreed that considering stakeholder's needs and priorities during strategic planning process influences performance in Turkana county government, 33% agreed, 7% were neutral, 13% disagreed while 12% strongly disagreed. This was supported by a mean of 3.124 and a standard deviation of 2.158. On whether stakeholder participation in strategic planning process influence performance in Turkana county government, 26% strongly agreed, 23% agreed, 7% were undecided on whether stakeholder participation in strategic planning process influences performance in Turkana county government, 27% disagreed and 17% strongly disagreed. The results were a bit balanced at a 2.981 mean and 1.745 standard deviation.

As to whether stakeholder feedback during strategic planning influence performance in Turkana county government, 27% of the respondents strongly agreed, 29% agreed, 10% were neutral, 21% disagreed while 13% strongly disagreed and indicated that indeed stakeholder feedback during strategic planning influence performance in Turkana county government at 2.987 mean and 1.526 standard deviation. Asked whether getting stakeholders to understand constituents of strategic planning influence performance in Turkana county government, 19% strongly agreed, 18% agreed that indeed getting stakeholders to understand constituents of strategic planning influence performance in Turkana county government. 6% remained neutral while 28% disagreed with the statement, 29% of the respondents strongly disagreed which implied that getting stakeholders to understand constituents of strategic planning influence performance in Turkana county government. These findings were at a mean of 3.420 and a standard deviation of 1.652.

4.2 Performance of Turkana County Government

The data presented in the table below concerned the data collected on the performance of Turkana County government and presented in the table below.

Table 2: Performance of Turkana County Government

	SA %	A %	N %	D %	SD %	Mean	STDEV
Turkana county government has enough resources to meet its obligations effectively	27	22	7	27	17	2.715	1.653
The county leadership motivates staff to work for the aim of higher organizational performance	35	22	5	20	18	3.015	1.544
Progress is documented and reviewed regularly, quarterly and annually by the county leadership	22	24	7	24	23	2.212	1.738
The county has a clear direction of where it is heading or where it wants to go as per the citizen feedback	23	24	8	23	22	2.106	1.566

Data was collected, analyzed and presented on the dependent variable (Performance of Turkana County government) as shown in the table above. The respondents' views as to whether Turkana county government had enough resources to meet its obligations effectively were that 27% strongly agreed, 22% agreed that indeed the county government had enough resources to meet its obligations effectively, 7% were neutral, 27% disagreed, while 17% strongly disagreed. From the data, the respondents were equally divided on this statement since the responses were split equally in the middle. With a mean of 2.715 and standard deviation of 1.653, there is need for further research on why the respondents reacted in this manner with only 7% appearing neutral.

On the statement about whether county leadership motivates staff to work for the aim of higher performance, 35% of the respondents strongly agreed, 22% agreed, 5% were neutral while 20% disagreed and 18% of the respondents strongly disagreed that county leadership motivates staff to work for the aim of higher performance. Majority of the respondents affirmed at 57% that indeed county leadership motivates staff to work for the aim of higher performance (Mean=3.015, STDEV=1.541). On whether progress is documented and reviewed regularly, quarterly and annually by the county leadership, 22% strongly agreed, 24% agreed, 7% remained neutral, 24% disagreed while 23% strongly disagreed that county progress is documented and reviewed regularly, quarterly and annually by the county leadership. Respondents were also equally divided on this statement with 46% returning on affirmative while 47% returning a negative verdict at mean= 2.212 and a standard deviation of 1.738. There is therefore need for further research on whether progress is documented and reviewed regularly, quarterly and annually by the county leadership.

Concerning whether the county has a clear direction of where it is heading or where it wants to go as per the citizen feedback, 23% of the respondents strongly agreed, 24% agreed, 8% remained neutral, 23% disagreed while 22% strongly disagreed that the county has no clear direction of where it is heading or where it wants to go as per the citizen feedback (Mean=2.106, STDEV=1.566). Generally, it appeared that the respondents were once more equally divided on whether the county has a clear direction of where it is heading or where it wants to go as per the citizen feedback. The equally negative and positive feedback on the three statements in this variable need further investigation while the respondents affirmed that the county leadership motivates staff to work for the aim of higher performance.

4.3 Correlation Analysis

Correlation analysis results were used for measuring the relationship among the variables, both dependent variable (Performance of Turkana County government) and independent variables (Stakeholder involvement, strategic resource allocation and strategic risk planning), and the results presented in the table below;

Table 3: Pearson Correlation Matrix

	Stakeholder Involvement	Performance
Stakeholder Involvement	1	.796**
Performance	.796**	1

**Correlation is Significant at .001 level (2-tailed). *Correlation is Significant at .05 level (2-tailed).

The table above presented the correlation results among study independent variables and dependent variable. The findings reflected a strong, direct and significant correlation among the variables for the study. The correlation results per independent variable in a descending order was; Shareholder Involvement $r=.812$ at $p<.01$ significance level. According to Kangogo and Merecia (2021), these results denoted a strong relationship between the independent variable strategic planning element and performance of Turkana County government.

4.4 Regression Analysis

Multiple linear regressions were computed to investigate how much change the independent variables influenced the dependent variable individually and collectively while the model summary presented regression coefficients that indicated how much variation observed in the dependent variable was a contribution of each independent variable when all other factors were held constant while the P values for the coefficients indicated whether these relationships were statistically significant. Study results were as presented below;

4.4.1 Model Summary

The coefficient of determination (R-squared) was used to identify the variance at which the independent variables explained the dependent variable in the model.

Table 4: Model Summary

Model	R	R-Square	Adjusted R-Square	Std Error of the Estimate
1	.800 ^a	.640	.634	.105

a. Predictors: (Constant), Stakeholder Involvement,

The Regression model revealed a coefficient of determination (R-Square) with a value of 0.640 signifying that the independent variables (Stakeholder Involvement) accounted for 64% of the changes witnessed in performance of Turkana county government. All other factors that affected performance and which were not the concern for this study accounted for 36% of the changes witnessed in performance of Turkana County government. Such factors were taken care of by way of the stochastic error term in the regression equation.

This had the implication that other than the strategic planning element, the county government needs to consider other factors that could complement and enhance performance of the county government. However, these factors were beyond the scope of this study so they were not explored. The regression parameters were displayed in the ANOVA model.

4.4.2 ANOVA

Table 5: ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	d.f	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	60.470	1	60.470	16.401	.000 ^b
	Residual	243.314	67	3.687		
	Total	303.784	68			

a. **Dependent Variable: Performance**

b. **Predictors: (Constant); Stakeholder Involvement,**

The Analysis of variance (ANOVA) output in table 4.12 revealed an F value of 16.401 which was greater than the F-critical value of 2.76 at the level of significance of 0.000. Given the p-value = 0.000, which is < 0.05 it indicated that the model was statistically significant in predicting how strategic planning elements influence performance of Turkana county government. This implied that the independent variables of the study were good predictors of performance of Turkana county government.

In the relationship between the independent variable as operationalized in the one factor and the dependent variable which is the performance is displayed in table 4.13 below;

4.4.3 Regression Coefficients

Data on the nature of the relationship among variables was as in the table below;

Table 6: Regression Coefficients

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		β	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	32.85	2.503		2.117	.000
	Stakeholder Involvement	.586	.015	.609	2.139	.001

a. P<.005, 95% Confidence level, N=68

From the study findings, the following regression model was extracted:

$$Y = 32.85 + .586X_1 + .e$$

The regression coefficients in the table above revealed how much is influenced in the dependent variable as a result of the individual independent variables while holding all other factors constant. From the study findings, a unit change in shareholder involvement led to a .586 unit change in performance of Turkana county government, (p-value = 0.001).

5. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Data analysis results revealed that considering stakeholder's needs and priorities during strategic planning process influenced performance in Turkana county government. Additionally, stakeholder participation in strategic planning process influenced performance in the county government. Stakeholder feedback during strategic planning influenced performance in Turkana county government while getting stakeholders to understand constituents of strategic planning did not influence performance in Turkana county government. The study made the following conclusions from the findings;

From the study findings, a unit change in shareholder involvement led to a .586 unit change in performance of Turkana county government, (p-value = 0.001). The following recommendations were made from the study findings; that stakeholder participation in strategic planning process should be fully incorporated in the county processes for better performance as well as emphasizing on stakeholder feedback during strategic planning for improved performance in Turkana county government. The county leadership should put measures in place to ensure that stakeholders are meant to understand constituents of strategic planning.

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